

Joint Placement and Scheduling for Time-Sensitive Applications in Edge Computing

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Abstract—In the dawn of the 6G era, edge computing environments have to cope with the increasing demands of next-generation cloud-native applications, such as time-sensitive applications. In this context, the application-graph placement problem is further exacerbated by the need to efficiently schedule time-sensitive traffic in order to meet stringent latency or other Quality of Service (QoS) requirements. This time-sensitive aspect, which is often overlooked, raises the need for a unified placement and scheduling approach.

To this end, we propose a holistic approach to the placement and scheduling problem for time-sensitive applications within edge computing facilities. In particular, we employ Constraint Programming (CP) to compute efficient solutions in a single step, avoiding the limitations stemming from the sequential execution of separate placement and scheduling solvers. Our solution is compliant with industrial Time-Sensitive Networking (TSN) standards (*i.e.*, IEEE 802.1 Qbv). A comparative evaluation among a range of CP variants sheds lights into various aspects, such as the gains stemming from the use of search heuristics.

I. INTRODUCTION

The evolution of edge computing and Internet-of-Things (IoT) empower the deployment of emerging IoT-enabled cloud-native applications for the various needs of verticals, such as energy, automotive, healthcare, and manufacturing [1], [2]. One aspect which is often met across such applications is time-sensitivity, as (portion of) their data needs to be delivered within certain deadlines. This requirement mandates a deterministic behavior from the network, which is often sought through Time-Sensitive Networking (TSN) specifications [3]–[10], such as IEEE 802.1 Qbv [8] which can sustain bounded latency and jitter for scheduled traffic. This TSN standard, in particular, relies on Centralized Network Controllers (CNCs) for the computation and population of scheduling entries onto the so-called Gate Control Lists (GCLs) in order to protect high-priority traffic from potential interference from other co-existing (non-time-sensitive) flows [6].

The deployment of time-sensitive applications onto edge cloud infrastructures entails additional complexity, since besides the need to optimize the placement of the application graph, TSN should be harnessed for the prioritization of time-sensitive traffic in switches. In fact, the placement and scheduling problems are highly dependent, since the former designates the paths where scheduling will be applied. Decoupling these problems with the aim of utilizing existing solutions in a sequential manner (*i.e.*, placement optimization followed by

schedule computation) can lead to various implications, as the placement optimizer is commonly oblivious of scheduling constraints. For instance, the selection of paths which substantial traffic interference may lead to the severe penalization of non-time-sensitive traffic by the scheduler in order to meet latency or other QoS requirements for time-sensitive flows.

Since the placement and scheduling problems are interconnected in the context of time-sensitive applications, we stress on the need for a unified approach. In particular, we seek to compute efficient solutions for the combined problem within a single step, taking into account constraints pertaining to placement and scheduling. To this end, we propose a constraint programming (CP) formulation that designates the mapping of application graphs onto an edge cloud infrastructure (*i.e.*, datacenter) and also computes the schedules on the TSN switches within the datacenter network. In terms of TSN, our solution complies with IEEE 802.1 Qbv (which comprises one of the most widely used industrial TSN standards), essentially computing the GCL configurations that need to be populated onto TSN switches for the prioritization and protection of time-sensitive traffic.

We conduct a comparative evaluation among different variants of our unified approach, assessing the impact of certain features commonly utilized in CP, such as search heuristics. In addition, we compare our solution with a decoupled approach where the application-graph placement and the TSN schedule computation are carried out as separate steps. The outcome of this comparison substantiates our claims (*i.e.*, need for a unified approach), as the decoupled approach fails to compute valid solutions for certain problem instances.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. In Section II, we elaborate on the description of the combined placement and scheduling problem. Section III introduces the mathematical model and CP formulation for the problem at hand. In Section IV, we evaluate the efficiency of the proposed solution using simulations. Finally, Section V highlights our conclusions.

II. PROBLEM DESCRIPTION

The deployment of time-sensitive applications on edge computing infrastructures, such as the edge datacenter illustrated in Fig. 1, entails various challenging aspects. To shed light on these aspects, we represent such an application as a graph. The application graph that is depicted in Fig. 1 has

specific delay budget requirements (e.g., 2 ms), composed of nodes that can express application components and/or Virtual Network Functions (VNF) between pairs of talkers and listeners (Fig. 1). These nodes are associated with CPU and memory demands, stemming from the resource profiles of each application component or VNF. The application graph can be further annotated with bandwidth demands of flows between talkers and listeners, as well as latency budgets (or potentially other QoS requirements) of time-sensitive flows.

The problem at hand is two-fold since both the application graph should be placed in an efficient manner (i.e., ensuring resource conservation, such as inter-rack bandwidth which is a relatively scarce resource in oversubscribed datacenter networks), whereas, at the same time, time-sensitive traffic should be scheduled within the network to meet latency or other QoS requirements. In the following, we briefly discuss the graph embedding and flow scheduling problems and stress on the need for a unified approach to the placement of time-sensitive application graphs and the schedule computation for time-sensitive traffic.

Graph Embedding. Graph embedding entails the assignment of application-graph nodes to computing nodes (i.e., servers), as well as the mapping of graph edges onto network paths, with the most common objective being resource efficiency, which is usually achieved through the minimization of the embedding footprint [11], [12]. This requires solving complex placement constraints, such as ensuring proximity between components to reduce delays, while accounting for the limited computing, storage, and network capacities, typical of edge computing environments. Furthermore, all placement decisions must comply with the latency constraints of (time-sensitive) flows.

Flow Scheduling. Flow scheduling is associated with the computation of transmission intervals among multiple traffic classes (or flows) over multi-queued switch ports. TSN has paved the way for meeting the requirements of scheduled traffic (i.e., bounded latency and jitter), through a set of standards, such as IEEE 802.1 Qbv (also known as Time-Aware Shaper – TAS) [8]. In this respect, each traffic class is assigned a specific transmission window, ensuring that packets from different traffic classes do not interfere with each other. The main challenge, hereby, lies in computing appropriate transmission windows for all time-sensitive traffic, while avoiding collisions as well as the severe penalization of non-time-sensitive flows.

Although the application-graph placement and flow scheduling can be addressed as individual problems, any approach that decouples these problems can lead to inefficient solutions. More precisely, as a placement optimization method is commonly unaware of scheduling requirements and constraints (e.g., transmission periods and delivery deadlines of time-sensitive flows, traffic interference at each hop), paths selected for time-sensitive flows may suffer from substantial traffic interference. In this case, flow migration(s) may be required to alleviate the load from these paths; otherwise, the flow

Fig. 1: Application graph placement onto a two-layer edge datacenter network.

scheduler will end up severely penalizing non-time-sensitive flows in order to sustain any bounds for time-sensitive traffic. Conversely, executing a scheduler beforehand may lead to scheduling computations over paths, whose allocation may be infeasible due to resource constraints (which the scheduler is oblivious of).

These implications essentially mandate a unified approach, where application component placement and flow scheduling are applied in a coordinated fashion (rather than individually), towards optimized solutions across the domains of graph embedding and scheduling. In Section III, we present a CP formulation that addresses this combined problem. Other related studies mainly seek to derive combined solutions tailored to industrial environments [13], [14]. Hence, we do not consider them directly comparable with our work.

III. PROBLEM FORMULATION

The approach that we follow in order to tackle the problem at hand is based on constraint programming (CP). The latter provides significant flexibility in terms of problem modeling, offering dedicated algorithms to handle patterns of constraints (global constraints) together with powerful constraint propagation techniques, as well as the ability to employ general search heuristics without sacrificing completeness. Thus, the problem is modeled as a set of decision variables, each one having a domain of values and a number of constraints on the former. Contrary to other approaches to NP problems, CP offers significant freedom in the constraint specification.

We assume a graph representation $G = (V, E)$ of an edge datacenter, where all components depicted in Fig. 1, i.e., servers and switches, are vertices (nodes n_i), while edges are links ($l_{ij} \in E$) connecting the former, i.e., link l_{ij} connects nodes n_i and n_j , respectively. Each graph node has a number of attributes that take constant values, i.e., fabric delay fd_i , node RAM n_i^{ram} and node CPU n_i^{cpu} , to accommodate application components. Since the latter can be hosted only in servers, node RAM and CPU in the case of switches are both equal to zero. This uniform representation of servers and switches allows for easily expressing allocation and routing

decisions in graphs of varying lengths. Link attributes include their propagation delay $d_{i,j}$, speed $sp_{i,j}$, and 8 queues $Q_{i,j}$, following the IEEE 802.1 Qbv standard [8].

A time-sensitive application i is defined by its application graph, which consists of a sequence of application components $ac_{i,j}$, where each component has a number of requirements in terms of RAM ($ac_{i,j}^{ram}$), CPU ($ac_{i,j}^{cpu}$) and a processing time $ac_{i,j}^{proc}$ (i.e., the time it takes application component to complete its processing on a packet). In the following, we refer to the set of applications to be scheduled as AP . In this work, we consider application graphs of fixed length $|C|$, without loss of generality, since the formulation can be easily extended to graphs of variable length. Thus,

$$A_i = [ac_{i,1}, ac_{i,2}, \dots, ac_{i,|C|}] \quad (1)$$

We denote the set CH as $CH = \{1..|C|\}$. A component $ac_{i,j}$ can be assigned to a server with sufficient resources, i.e., to a node k , such that $ac_{i,j}^{ram} \leq n_k^{ram} \wedge ac_{i,j}^{cpu} \leq n_k^{cpu}$.

Each time-sensitive application i is also related to a flow f_i , which determines the rate and size of data that needs to be processed by the application. Following the standard formulation of periodic flows found in TSN scheduling research [15], [16], [17], [18], we assume single-packet flows, with a packet size p_i such that it fits into a single Ethernet frame, with a delay budget df_i (deadline), and a period T_i that determines the frequency of the transmission. Note that the deadline in this case must also take into account the processing time of each component ($ac_{i,j}^{proc}$) in the chain.

A flow f_i is related to a path P_i , that is a sequence of nodes, i.e., servers and switches. We consider paths of variable length; however, since we refer to two-layer datacenter topologies, where the hop-count between any pair of racks is 4 (as in Fig. 1), the maximum length of such a path can be easily determined to be equal to $|P| = 4 * (|C| - 1) + 1$, with the later being the worst case scenario where components of the application reside in different racks in the edge datacenter. Thus, a path consists of nodes $pn_{i,k}$ as in Eq. (2):

$$P_i = [pn_{i,1}, pn_{i,2}, \dots, pn_{i,|P|}] \quad (2)$$

where $pn_{i,k} \in V, k \in 1..|P|$. We denote the set PT , as $PT = \{1..|P|\}$. Such a path must be valid, i.e., given a graph $G = (V, E)$, for every pair of consecutive nodes in the path $(pn_{i,k}, pn_{i,k+1})$ there must be a link $l_{pn_{i,k}, pn_{i,k+1}} \in E$. Discovery of the appropriate path is one of the objectives of the model, thus, the paths P_i are problem decision variables.

Each component $ac_{i,j}$ is mapped to one node in the path P_i , thus, the constraint in Eq. (3) holds:

$$\forall i \in AP, j \in CH, \exists k \in PT : ac_{i,j} = pn_{i,k} \quad (3)$$

where k is the index of the node in the path sequence where the application component is mapped to, we set $k = (ac_{i,j}^{Index})$ and in order to simplify the expression of constraints in the following $ac_{i,j}^{Node} = pn_{i,k}$, i.e., $ac_{i,j}^{Node}$ will receive as a value a node from V . An example of this mapping is depicted in Fig. 2, where the application graph is mapped to a subset of

Fig. 2: Mapping of application components to a path. Nodes NO_NODE correspond to dummy nodes.

the nodes of the path. The figure also depicts the allocation solution, i.e., servers and switches that form the complete path, as the latter is presented in Fig. 1.

Since we consider paths of variable length, the set of $ac_{i,j}^{Index}$ will act as decision variables. Obviously, $\forall i \in AP, ac_{i,1} = pn_{i,1}$. In order to ensure a correct mapping, a number of constraints must hold. The following constraint (Eq. 4) preserves the order of components and ensures that each component is mapped to a different server node in the path.

$$\forall i \in AP, j, l \in CH | j < l : ac_{i,j}^{Index} < ac_{i,l}^{Index} \quad (4)$$

Finally, for every server that appears in the path, there must be exactly one application component that points to it, leading to the constraint in Eq. (5):

$$\forall i \in AP, k \in PT : (pn_{i,k}^{ram} > 0) \rightarrow \sum_{j=1}^{|C|} (ac_{i,j}^{Index} = k) = 1 \quad (5)$$

In the notation above, we assume the standard boolean to integer conversion, common in constraint programming, i.e., that a value of a boolean condition is zero in the case it is false and one in the case it is true.

The above constraints are sufficient in order to compute a valid path for the application. Note that in order to host paths of varying length, we introduce a dummy node (i.e., NO_NODE), to which all server nodes are linked. For instance, in Fig. 2, the application graph has a length of 3, thus the maximum path length is 9; however, the solution depicted involves only 7 active nodes (i.e., servers and switches), leading to the introduction of two dummy nodes at the end of the chain. Dummy nodes have all their attributes (i.e., fabric delay, RAM, CPU) equal to zero.

For any placement to be valid, the assignment has to respect the capacity constraints of nodes in the path, leading to the constraints in Eq. (6) and Eq. (7) for RAM and CPU, respectively:

$$\forall n_k \in V : \sum_{i \in A, j \in CH} (ac_{i,j}^{ram} * (ac_{i,j}^{Node} = n_k)) \leq n_k^{ram} \quad (6)$$

$$\forall n_k \in V : \sum_{i \in A, j \in CH} (ac_{ij}^{cpu} * (ac_{ij}^{node} = n_k)) \leq n_k^{cpu} \quad (7)$$

The constraints in Eq. (6) and Eq. (7) can be easily modeled using the *global bin packing* constraint, which is supported by many CP solvers.

However, placement decisions are also affected by TSN scheduling decisions [13], *i.e.*, the path must be such that the deadline df_i for application i is respected. The task is to determine a feasible scheduling pattern for the flows with respect to their latency requirements.

Given the path P_i of nodes (Eq. 2) that application components are mapped to, we associate with each node $pn_{i,j}$ in the path P_i a start transmission time $S_{i,j}$, which is the time point relative to the start of the TSN schedule (time point 0). Thus, a flow $f_i, i \in AP$ on a path P_i of length $|P|$ can be modeled as a set of operations $1..|P|$, each having a start time (offset) *i.e.*, the set $\{S_{i,1}, S_{i,2}, \dots, S_{i,|P|}\}$ where each variable $S_{i,j} | j \in PT$ represents the start time of the transmission of the packet of flow i on the node j . We refer to these start times as the *primary flow*, following previous work on TSN flow scheduling [15], [18].

We follow a similar approach to modeling the TSN scheduling problem in constraint programming, as those in [15], [16], [17], extending the model presented in [18].

For each flow f_i we define a queue Q_i , which is considered to be the same for all links of the flow. Scheduling of flows that have different periods occurs in a time domain defined by the *hyperperiod* [16], where the latter is defined as the least common multiple of all flow periods, *i.e.*, $HP = lcm(T_i | i \in AP)$, thus flows may occur multiple times in a hyperperiod. In the latter case, each flow f_i that occurs $M = HP/T_i$ times in the hyperperiod, consists of $N * M$ start times, as indicated in Eq. (8):

$$f_i = \{S_{i,1}, \dots, S_{i,|P|}, \\ S_{i,|P|+1}, \dots, S_{i,2*|P|}, \\ \dots \\ S_{i,|P|*(M-1)+1}, \dots, S_{i,M*|P|}\} \quad (8)$$

As in [18], we define subflows $S_{i,j} | j > |P|$ as *secondary flows* (mentioned as flow occurrences in [15]). This distinction stems from the fact that primary flow decision variables and those of the secondary flow participate in different constraints in the model. Secondary flows share the same path with primary flows, *i.e.*, the same nodes are involved.

The zero jitter requirement imposes that the time difference in the corresponding variables in each secondary subflow is the same, *i.e.*, primary and secondary subflows are linked by the constraint in Eq. (9):

$$\forall i \in AP, j \in 1..|P|, m \in 2..M \\ S_{i,j} + (m-1) * T_i = S_{i,|P|*(m-1)+j} \quad (9)$$

Additionally, for each node in the path P_i , we maintain an *arrival time* $Arr_{i,o}$, *i.e.*, the time that the packet has arrived at the node from the previous node in its path. Thus:

$$\forall i \in AP, j \in PT | j > 1, \\ Arr_{i,j} = S_{i,j-1} + d_{l_{i,j-1,j}} + \left\lceil \frac{P_i}{sp_{l_{i,j-1,j}}} \right\rceil \quad (10)$$

In Eq. (10), we are abusing the notation and denote as $l_{i,j-1,j}$ the link connecting nodes $pn_{i,j-1}$ and $pn_{i,j}$, *i.e.*, the link $l_{pn_{i,j-1}, pn_{i,j}}$. The equation factors in the propagation delay $d_{l_{i,j-1,j}}$ of the link connecting the nodes and the transmission delay, the latter computed as the ceiling of the packet size over the speed of the link $\lceil \frac{P_i}{sp_{l_{i,j-1,j}}} \rceil$. For the initial node in the path, the arrival time is zero, *i.e.*, $Arr_{j,1} = 0$ since we assume that each packet transmitted by the source (*e.g.*, IoT device) is ready at the first node during the start of the overall schedule. Arrival times are computed for the secondary flows as well, and a similar constraint to that in Eq. (9) is included in the model, linking primary and secondary flows.

Arrival times allow for easily defining *ordering* constraints, ensuring that a packet is transmitted by a node after it has arrived and properly processed, leading to the constraint in Eq. (11).

$$\forall i \in AP, \forall j \in PT, \\ Arr_{i,j} + fd_{pn_{i,j}} + d_{i,j}^{proc} \leq S_{i,j} \quad (11)$$

Constraint Eq. (11) considers both the fabric delay $fd_{pn_{i,j}}$ (introduced by the node) and the processing delay $d_{i,j}^{proc}$ incurred by the application component execution on a server. The processing delay in the case of switches is equal to zero (Eq. 12).

$$d_{i,j}^{proc} = \begin{cases} ac_{il}^{proc} & j = ac_{il}^{index} \\ 0 & otherwise \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

It should be noted that the constraint in Eq. (11) is enforced only in primary flow decision variables, since the equality constraints of Eq. (9) will ensure that the correct time distance is maintained among operations of each subflow.

Given that each application flow has a deadline, the flow's packet must complete its processing in the final node of the path P_i (which is bound to be a server), before the deadline df_i :

$$\forall i \in AP, Arr_{i, ac_{i|C|}^{index}} + ac_{i|C|}^{proc} \leq df_i \quad (13)$$

where $ac_{i|C|}^{proc}$ is the processing time of the last application component in the graph. Once again, enforcement of the deadline constraint is imposed only on primary flows, with the equality constraints of Eq. (9) ensuring the former in the hyperperiod.

An node egress link transmits a single packet at each time point, thus, there must be no overlapping between two transmissions on the same link. Since arrival times, as defined in Eq. (10), signify the end of the transmission process, the

constraint in Eq. (14) ensures that a link is only used by a single flow:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \forall i, l \in AP, j, m \in CPT, i < l | l_{i,j,j+1} = l_{l,m,m+1} : \\
& S_{l,m} \geq Arr_{i,j+1} \\
& \vee \\
& S_{i,j} \geq Arr_{l,m+1}
\end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

where $l_{i,j,j+1}$ is the egress link of flow i on node $pn_{i,j}$, whereas CPT denotes the complete path, *i.e.*, the set of all primary and secondary application flows. Note that constraint (14) is enforced in all decision variables of both primary and secondary flows.

Finally, in the case of switches, a frame must be fully received before being copied to its destination queue and since frames are transmitted according to their reception order, packets addressed to the same egress link should arrive in the correct order; *otherwise*, they are forced to be placed in different queues. The latter is referred to as the *frame isolation* constraint and is modeled by the disjunction in Eq. (15):

$$\begin{aligned}
& \forall i, l \in AP, j, m \in CPT, i < l | l_{i,j,j+1} = l_{l,m,m+1} : \\
& \left((Q_i = Q_l) \Rightarrow \right. \\
& \quad (S_{i,j} < S_{l,m} \Leftrightarrow Arr_{i,j} < Arr_{l,m}) \wedge \\
& \quad \left. (S_{i,j} > S_{l,m} \Leftrightarrow Arr_{i,j} > Arr_{l,m}) \right) \\
& \vee \\
& Q_i \neq Q_l
\end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

The constraint in Eq. (15) ensures that the reception of the frame that needs to be transmitted first is completed before the reception of the second frame. Such a constraint is implemented using *reified constraints*, offered by most CP solvers.

The model described above is implemented using MiniZinc [19], an open-source expressive constraint modeling language that offers model compilation and execution on a number of different back-end solvers. Our choice was dictated by the fact that MiniZinc supports the compilation of global constraints, such as the *element* constraint, the *bin packing* constraint, reified constraints, as well as a range of variable/value ordering general heuristics for finding solutions, which proved more than adequate to implement the model. In the next section, we present evaluation results from our proposed model.

IV. EVALUATION

In order to provide an evaluation of the model presented, we consider a topology that involves 4 racks of servers, and 3 root switches. We set the fabric delay of root and rack switches to 3 μs and 4 μs respectively, while the *farbric* delay of servers is set to 1 μs . Links between servers and their corresponding Top-of-the-Rack (ToR) switch have a capacity of 100 Mbps, whereas links between ToR and root switches have a capacity of 1 Gbps.

TABLE I: Results for first solution (10 servers/rack, $|C| = 4$)

F	No heuristics			Heuristic		
	<i>Runtime</i>	<i>Hops</i>	<i>Latency</i>	<i>Runtime</i>	<i>Hops</i>	<i>Latency</i>
3	16.66	14.1	2654.4	15.94	13.6	2676.6
4	22.37	15.4	3462.3	21.19	16	3491
5	42.24	20.9	4371.4	39.3	20.9	4371.4
6	47.78	25.9	5254.3	43.72	25.8	5244.9

In order to gain insights into the efficiency of the proposed unified placement and scheduling model, we conduct experiments involving a varying number of servers in each rack (*i.e.*, from 4 to 10), and a varying number of flows to be scheduled with a diverse number of chain lengths in each flow. Each service function has a varying demand in terms of CPU and RAM, as well as a varying processing time.

In terms of metrics, we consider the total *number of hops* in each solution (*i.e.*, the number of switches that appear in all paths P_i) and the total *latency* of the flows, given by the completion time of the data processing of each flow. The first metric essentially lets us quantify the application graph embedding footprint; lower values imply a higher degree of application component co-location. The latency metric provides an indication of the tax that the allocation and TSN scheduling impose on the delay budget of the application.

We leverage on MiniZinc for the introduction of *general* search heuristics, commonly used in CP problems. More specifically, we opt for assigning decision variables regarding the paths P_i of the applications, *i.e.*, allocating application components to nodes, selecting paths, and subsequently assigning decision variables regarding the start times of the primary flows. In both cases, the value selection strategy consists in assigning to the decision variable the *min* value in its domain first. It should be noted that variable/value selection heuristics do not affect the completeness of the search process, *i.e.*, no solutions are discarded. In all our tests, as a back-end solver we utilize OR-Tools CP-Sat, which is considered as a state-of-the-art solver.

We initially quantify the potential benefits stemming from the utilization of the specific search heuristics mentioned above, when returning the first solution obtained during the search. Table I presents a comparison between the non-heuristic and heuristic models with 10 servers per rack and a variable number of flows (column F), each traversing 4 application components. Column *Runtime* presents the total time (sec) to compute a solution (*i.e.*, both the MiniZinc compilation and solver runtime), column *Hops* indicates the average number of hops, whereas column *Latency* represents the value of the respective metric. The results presented have been averaged across 10 different problems for the different number of flows. The tests are conducted on a virtual machine with 16 virtual CPUs and 12 GB of RAM, running Ubuntu 22.04 LTS.

As depicted in Table I, the heuristic CP variant, which assigns paths first, yields some benefits in terms of runtime at the expense of a minor impact on the two efficiency

metrics under consideration (*i.e.*, hop-count and latency). The reduction in solver runtime becomes more prevalent as the number of flows increases. Similar results are obtained for other combinations of servers (per rack) and flows.

Next, we investigate how the model behaves when seeking optimal solutions. Note that the complexity class of the problem at hand is NP. More precisely, each problem that we solve, *i.e.*, the TSN scheduling problem which can be considered as a job-shop scheduling problem, as well as the resource allocation problem, both fall into the NP class. The complete search procedure used in CP guarantees optimality at the expense of solver runtime, in comparison to non-optimal methods. An important aspect of problems such as the one we are dealing with is *symmetry*, *i.e.*, there are multiple solutions which are syntactically different, albeit being essentially the same. For instance, consider the case of a chain composed of two services S_1 and S_2 assigned to two servers A and B in the same rack; there are two solutions in this case, $S_1 \rightarrow A, S_2 \rightarrow B$ and $S_1 \rightarrow B, S_2 \rightarrow A$, both solutions are of equal value. The same observation applies for paths under the existence of multiple root switches (common in datacenter network topologies).

Table II illustrates the results from optimal solutions on diverse instances of the problem. The optimization model leads to a notable reduction in the hop-count and latency at the cost of prolonged solver runtime, compared to the CP variant that returns the first solution. Note that the better values of both efficiency metrics reflect the joint optimization achieved by our proposed model, *i.e.*, the small hop-count represents a small embedding footprint, while the low latency is crucial in terms of time-sensitivity. It can be observed that the reduction of the latency is not on par with the reduction of the hop-count, when comparing between the first and corresponding optimal solution. This stems from the fact that the overall latency (as appearing in Table II) encompasses a processing delay within each server hosting application components, which is incurred irrespective of the reduction of the hop-count. On the other hand, the increased runtime for optimal solutions can be, in part, attributed to the symmetries in the problem, *i.e.*, in several cases, the delay incurred by the solver to prove the optimality of the solution is greater than the time required to reach this optimal solution.

To substantiate our claim that the combined approach indeed contributes towards an efficient solution to the problem at hand, we conduct a set of experiments decoupling the two phases, *i.e.*, application-graph placement and flow scheduling. To this end, we first compute an optimal placement of the application graph with respect to the number of hops, minimizing the latter, under the server CPU capacity and memory constraints, targeting a solution with an increased probability of respecting flow deadlines. Given these computed placements, we employ part of the solver to derive the TSN schedules on the flows. Interestingly, in 69 out of the 320 total tests that we conduct, no valid schedule has been identified. Since the CP approach is *complete*, each such result signifies that there is no valid schedule for the specific optimal hop

TABLE II: Results for first and optimal solutions ($|C| = 3$)

S	F	First Solution			Optimal		
		Runtime	Hops	Latency	Runtime	Hops	Latency
4	3	3.75	12.7	1789.3	4.08	5.8	1653.4
4	4	8.97	15.1	2444.6	10.17	7.9	2326.2
4	5	13.86	20.4	3154.1	53.86	12.4	2982.8
4	6	23.22	17.0	2968.0	99.44	6.0	2149.0
6	3	4.78	7.1	1788.6	5.19	5.9	1769.2
6	4	10.16	8.7	2338.0	13.23	7.9	2325.2
6	5	16.9	13.5	2987.9	39.31	9.9	2927.2
6	6	24.43	17.7	3617.9	151.46	11.8	3469.1
8	3	6.65	8.0	1809.5	7.13	5.9	1746.2
8	4	10.13	11.5	2389.9	12.24	7.8	2286.4
8	5	16.02	12.7	2980.0	66.18	9.8	2888.4
8	6	29.8	17.2	3718.8	253.3	11.7	3547.7
10	3	8.06	6.0	1716.0	8.54	6.0	1716.0
10	4	13.67	10.2	2360.6	23.67	7.8	2255.4
10	5	20.26	13.5	2969.3	94.0	9.8	2859.4
10	6	28.41	14.6	3479.4	152.62	11.6	3377.1

placement computed. As a note, the MiniZinc model, which combines the two phases, manages to derive solutions for the entire range of 320 tests.

To gain insights into the quality of the solutions obtained, Table III illustrates the hop-count and latency of the decoupled and combined solution for a wide range of servers (per rack) and number of flows. The *chain length* remains equal to 3 ($|C| = 3$). Note that, in this table, we have included only the results of the problem instances for which the decoupled approach has managed to compute a valid solution.

It can be observed that in almost all cases, both approaches generate solutions with the same number of hops. However, in a few problem instances, the optimal solution yields slightly lower latency (indicated in bold in the respective column). Although this might seem to be unexpected at a first glance, there exist multiple allocations with the same number of hops, since the components of an application-graph can be assigned to different servers, while maintaining the total length of the path. However, this does not exclude a variance in terms of latency among these assignments. In some cases, the optimal solution with respect to latency is also associated with a higher hop-count. We suspect that this is due to assigning too many flows on a single path, leading to increased latency. This aspect certainly requires further investigation in an experimental environment, which we leave for future work.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we proposed a unified approach for the deployment of time-sensitive applications on edge computing infrastructures, addressing two challenging problems, *i.e.*, the placement of application graphs and the computation of TSN schedules based on the IEEE 802.1 Qbv standard. To this end, we presented a CP formulation for the joint optimization of both problems, in contrast to most studies that address these problems independently.

In our evaluation, we investigated the performance of different CP solver variants, aiming to strike a balance between efficiency and solver runtime. In this respect, a CP solver

TABLE III: Results from the decoupled and combined approach

Servers	No Flows	Decoupled Solution		Combined Solution	
		Hops	Latency	Hops	Latency
4	3	5.8	1644.8	5.8	1644.8
4	4	7.9	2318.2	7.9	2318.2
4	5	12.2	3026.0	12.5	2994.2
6	3	5.9	1769.2	5.9	1769.2
6	4	7.9	2325.2	7.9	2325.2
6	5	9.9	2920.2	9.9	2920.2
6	6	11.8	3499.2	11.8	3480.4
8	3	6.0	1779.8	6.0	1769.9
8	4	7.9	2350.7	7.9	2302.7
8	5	9.8	2895.2	9.8	2873.2
8	6	11.7	3511.7	11.7	3498.3
10	3	6.0	1716.0	6.0	1716.0
10	4	7.8	2302.4	7.8	2242.2
10	5	9.8	2917.8	9.8	2869.9
10	6	11.7	3515.1	11.7	3491.1

variant with search heuristics yields perceptible efficiency gains, as it computes embeddings with small footprints and low latency, inline with the main objectives of the placement and scheduling problems. Furthermore, we shedded light on the benefits stemming from our combined approach through a comparison against a solution that decouples the placement from the schedule computation. The associated results corroborate the superiority of the combined approach, which successfully manages to derive solutions for all problem instances, as opposed to the decoupled approach that was able to compute feasible solutions only for a subset of our tests.

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